

PRESSURE LEVEL ON MARGINAL GUMS, SOFT TISSUES AND PERIODONTAL TISSUES IN THE PROSTHESIS AREA

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Relevance of the study. The following scientific results have been obtained in the world, including the development and optimization of various methods of prosthetics using dentures: changes in clinical and immunological parameters, formation and course of inflammatory processes in the gums (King's College London, England); a method of various combined surgical treatment of dentures using dentures has been developed (University of Gothenburg, Sweden); It has been proven that in case of poor fitting of dental implants, the cause is the presence of various microflora in the oral cavity (Tokyo Medical and Dental University, Japan); various effective modern methods of prosthetics using dentures have been improved (University of Bern, Switzerland). To date, a number of research projects are being carried out in the world to improve various methods of prosthetics using dentures, including in the following priority areas: Improvement of methods for diagnosing the condition of oral tissues; development of new models of dentures; development of non-removable orthopedic prostheses; determination of materials of non-removable orthopedic prostheses and their physico-chemical properties; development of structural prostheses with various sets; improvement of modern technologies in dental prosthetics.

According to the authors, Saravi et al. International Journal of Implant Dentistry (2020), a review and systematic search conducted in accordance with the recommendations of PRISMA. The search revealed 2,237 studies, of which 6 studies were included in the qualitative analysis. It was found that the marginal loss of bone tissue after orthopedic treatment with a basic tooth in dentures is not related to the shape of the prosthesis. In the articles of researchers from Hadas University (Israel), the level of bone tissue from the mesial and distal sides of dentures was measured directly on the day of prosthesis implantation, 3 and 6 months after installation, a year after radiography. According to the one-stage and two-stage protocol, there was no difference in the rate of reduction of marginal bone loss and the survival rate of the base teeth, which was 100% [1.3.5.7.9].

International Journal of Implant Dentistry The International Journal of Implantological Dentistry (2020) has determined the accuracy of denture installation by comparing computed tomography images. A retrospective analysis of the needs of patients who applied to the dental center of the Bukhara State Medical Institute in 2015-2019 was carried out. It was revealed that with age, not only the absolute number of missing teeth increases, but also the number of defects that appear increases. Researchers in Uzbekistan have introduced the production of dental implants with biofilm based on tricalcium phosphate and chitosan, which have shown safety and good engraftment. Literature data on the rehabilitation of patients with secondary dentition defects using various dental floss models and orthopedic treatment show good results according to the analysis. However, there remains an urgent problem of determining the criteria for choosing denture models by evaluating their immunological, functional characteristics of the oral cavity, their osseointegration in accordance with the condition of the soft tissues of the bone and jaw.

Research objective. The optimal type of prosthesis was selected based on a comparative assessment of the effect of cermet and zirconium prostheses on the oral mucosa and local immune factors.

Materials and methods of a research. There were 214 patients (141 women and 73 men) and 30

healthy people aged 20 to 70 years living in Bukhara on the basis of the Scientific and Practical Center of Dentistry of the Bukhara State Medical Institute.

Results of a research and their discussion. Diagnostic monitoring of the periodontal condition was carried out before and after the installation of metal-ceramic and zirconium coatings, as well as for 1, 3, 6, 12 months after primary and repeated prosthetics in the area of the location of the base teeth.

In phase II, we conducted a study of 214 patients in the period from 2019 to 2021 who had no pronounced concomitant visceral pathology, defects in the dentition and hard tissues of the teeth, as well as VZP. Of these, 141 are women, which is 65.9%, and 73 are men - 34.1%, respectively. Gingivitis was detected in 30.4% (65 people), CPLS - 44.4% (95 people), CPSS - 17.8% (38 people), CPTS - 7.4% of cases in patients with defects of dentition and hard tissues of teeth [2.4.6.8.10.12.13].

The prevalence of defects in dentition and hard tooth tissues was analyzed, taking into account age and gender differences in patients with inflammatory periodontal diseases. We identified 25 people (11.7%) in the group of patients 20-30 years old, with defects of dentures and hard tissues of teeth, as well as VZP, in the group of patients 31-40 years old - 44 people (20.5%), in the group of patients 41-50 years old revealed that 28 people (13.1%), in the group of patients older than 50 years - 117 people (54.7%). Patients with metal-ceramic prostheses have local immune antigens (intolerance to metal alloys), increased permeability of the oral mucosa as a result of an active reaction to the traumatic effects of the prosthetic bed, which leads to the development of inflammatory processes in the oral fluid. Positive dynamics of indicators of local immunity of oral fluid was observed in patients with zirconium prostheses [9.11.12.13].

The foci of inflammation resulting from the exposure of the prosthesis were not observed during the examination, and it was found that their satisfactory regeneration was formed due to the complete adaptation of the tooth tissues to the prosthesis.

Conclusions. Structures of various designs (die-welded structures, structures with plastic coating, bridges made of stainless steel and bridges coated with titanium dioxide) with high values of electrochemical potentials (120-150 mV) unsatisfactory changes in surface hygiene, tooth-stem with adverse effects on the oral mucosa and marginal periodontal.

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